

JOINT PATHOLOGY IN MUSCLE-SKELETAL LUMBAR PAIN.

Mustayev Shahjakh

student of 517 group of therapy faculty

Samarkand State Medical University

Mirzayev Saidakhror

student of 517 group of therapy faculty

Samarkand State Medical University

Azimiva Aziza

student of 420 group of therapy faculty

Samarkand State Medical University

Abstract: Musculoskeletal (nonspecific) low back pain (lumbodynia), often with spread to the leg lumboischialgia, is one of the most common reasons for seeking medical advice and temporary disability of the population. In many cases, the development of pain is associated with lesions of the lumbar facet joints (FS) and the sacroiliac joint.

Keywords: musculoskeletal, myofascial, risk factors, lumbar, sacral spine.

Musculoskeletal pain (MSP) is extremely common and accounts for approximately one third of all acute and chronic pain syndromes. Their localization is very diverse, but the most favorite places are the lumbar and sacral spine, lower legs, shoulder girdle and neck. At the same time, in half of patients with MBS, pain occurs in several areas at once. SMB can occur at any age, both in the elderly and in young, able-bodied people; they are often found among students and schoolchildren. Patients suffering from pain experience

permanent restrictions on motor activity, which drastically reduces their quality of life, professional and household activities worsen. Thus, pain is not only a medical but also a social problem.

MBS (myofascial) occurs due to dysfunction of skeletal (striated) muscle tissue associated with muscle overload and muscle spasm. The underlying causes of this muscle spasm can be very diverse. Muscles respond with tension to any pathological impulse, being a non-specific indicator of the pathological process, which is why myofascial pain is so common. This type of pain can be associated not only with the pathology of the vertebral segments or extra vertebral structures (joints, ligamentous apparatus, etc.), but also with the pathology of internal organs. The latter should be of particular concern. Almost any somatic pathology can be accompanied by myofascial pain syndrome, since pain impulses from the affected organ lead to protective tension in the surrounding muscles. Therefore, identifying the causes of myofascial pain always requires a detailed analysis: complaints, anamnesis of life and diseases of the patient, general somatic, neurological, orthopedic and mental status data. Only with the exclusion of severe somatic pathology, such as tumors and metastases, abscesses, infectious and other diseases, can we speak of "benign" MSP.

A prerequisite for the development of such SMBs are functional disorders in the musculoskeletal system and failure to compensate for the natural age-related aging processes. Risk factors for the development of SMS include:

- ❖ age;
- ❖ engaging in heavy physical labor (especially prolonged static loads, lifting weights, turning the body and vibration);
- ❖ psychosocial aspects (monotonous work, dissatisfaction with working conditions);
- ❖ anxiety-depressive disorders;
- ❖ obesity;

- ❖ smoking;
- ❖ drug addiction
- ❖ severe scoliosis;
- ❖ history of headaches.

MBS is characterized by both acute and chronic pain syndromes. The primary pain that occurs is usually acute, sharp, intense, it disappears when the irritant is eliminated and the damaged tissue or organ is restored. This pain performs a protective function, warns the body of danger and ensures the activation of systems aimed at eliminating the damaging factor. However, pain does not always occur in response to damage: often it has already been eliminated, but the pain remains, being no longer a protective, but a damaging factor in the body. A component of such "pathological pain" is necessarily present in patients with chronic pain syndromes. Chronic pain often becomes an independent disease, being the only symptom that bothers the patient for a long time, and often its cause cannot be determined. Chronic pain affects an average of 15–20% of the population and is most commonly associated with musculoskeletal problems.

The occurrence of pain is an alarming signal of the body that a problem is developing in a certain area. Many reasons can lead to the occurrence of such discomfort. The most common culprits are degenerative-dystrophic processes (osteochondrosis, arthrosis), as well as various injuries, whether it be bruises, torn ligaments, or even just sprains or overstrain of untrained muscles. Excessive loads on the elements of the musculoskeletal system or their physiological aging provokes the development of diseases. Therefore, even minor pains can be harbingers or causes of serious problems. Timely access to a doctor and proper treatment will allow: to prevent the progression of the pathology, relieve pain, prevent the occurrence of complications, as well as improve the prognosis of treatment and, in most cases, it will be possible to recover or achieve stable

remission and prevent the disease from developing further. This improves the quality of life and restores working capacity.

Pain syndrome of any localization, which has arisen for any reason, can start a "chain reaction" called myofascial pain syndrome. A person intuitively tries to choose the most comfortable position during pain, and even the usual movements are performed differently - those muscles that were previously used to a lesser extent begin to be actively involved. The body seeks to create a muscular frame in order to immobilize the painful area. Subsequently, it is precisely those muscles that have taken on an additional load that cause the occurrence of myofascial pain syndrome. Myofascial pain syndrome (MBS) is a chronic, pathological condition caused by the formation of local muscle spasms or indurations represented by pain points (triggers). Pain can be provoked by pressing on these points, or by the movement of the muscles involved in the pathological process. This syndrome leads to limited range of motion and increased muscle fatigue.

When MBS occurs, pain spreads through the muscles from the source to the surrounding soft tissues, which is manifested by the appearance of new painful seals (pain points). These areas of muscle compaction are not large and have a diameter of 0.1-0.3 cm, but if a large number of them appear, they are grouped, thereby creating a trigger zone with a diameter of 1 cm or more. The appearance of pain points occurs with overstrain and microtraumatization of the muscle. MBS can cause a violation of the normal distribution of loads in the nearest joints and lead to early wear and even deformation (curvature).

Predisposing factors for the appearance of MBS are:

Pathology of the spine. Degenerative-dystrophic diseases (osteochondrosis of any localization, arthrosis of the intervertebral joints), spinal injuries are a source of pain that provokes the back muscles to maintain an

increased tone. Also, a factor provoking the occurrence of SMEs becomes a forced, due to pain, static position, which causes muscle strain.

Pathology of the musculoskeletal system. spinal deformity, asymmetry of the lower extremities (one-sided shortening), asymmetry (skew) of the pelvis, transverse and longitudinal flat feet can lead to an incorrect, uneven distribution of the load on the muscles, as well as cartilage and bones of the body, which will determine the occurrence of not only MBS, but also diseases such as arthrosis, arthritis, synovitis, laumontites. 70% of the population has scoliotic spinal deformity and 50% flat feet of varying degrees. Forced posture. Work in a monotonous position of the body, fixation of limbs, static position lead to muscle overload stereotyped movements. The same repetitive movements occur with the contraction of the same muscles, leading to their overstrain and improper distribution of tone. Inadequate loading, especially of untrained muscles. As a result, muscle strain and micro tears occur bruises. Direct trauma to the muscle itself causes a violation of the structure of its fibers. The consequence of this is a violation of the function, if the function of some fiber's decreases, then the function of others should increase, compensating for the lack of the first, which leads to an overload of the latter. Somatic diseases. Soreness of the internal organs, provokes tonic tension of certain muscle groups. With prolonged persistence of the pain syndrome, trigger points and chronic severe pain syndrome may form. Emotional overstrain. Various psycho-emotional reactions, such as stress, anxiety, can induce muscles to tonic tension. In turn, the occurrence of muscular-tonic states, and their persistence after an emotional experience, are capable of forming MBS and the gradual development of chronic back pain (osteocondrosis) radiating to the limbs. As a result of microtrauma or muscle overload, there is a violation of the transport of substances through the cell.

Calcium ions are released, which leads to damage at the cellular level. An excess amount of calcium provokes the contraction of the myocyte (muscle

cell). A muscle that is in a spasmodic state provides an increase in intramuscular pressure, which leads to a deterioration in microcirculation. With a long contraction, a large amount of work is performed, for which energy is expended, a period of relaxation is required to replenish energy. If there is no relaxation period for a long time, compensation mechanisms work: the energy in the cell is replenished not at the expense of newly arrived nutrients from the bloodstream, but at the expense of the available reserves inside itself, which leads to inefficient work. An even longer load, exceeding the capabilities of the muscle, causes a breakdown of compensatory mechanisms - the accumulation of toxins in the muscle tissue, and as a result, the formation of a trigger point. The resulting pain provokes muscle contraction. A vicious circle is formed: pain - muscle tension - pain. Also, a violation of the structure of the cartilage of the joint and bone can join this circle. When the pain spreads through the muscles, nerves can be involved, through which the pain syndrome can be transmitted to remote areas (for example, to give to the arms or legs with pain in the spine).

There are active and latent trigger points. Active pain points can appear during movement and even at rest. Latent points do not hurt at rest, but when you press them, a sharp pain occurs. There are 3 forms of myofascial pain syndrome: acute, subacute and chronic. In the acute form, the pain syndrome is maintained constantly and intensifies with movements. The subacute form is characterized by pain only during movements, and does not manifest itself at rest. In the chronic form of MBS, pain occurs only when the trigger point itself is pressed directly, and a feeling of discomfort may appear during movements.

Understanding the cause of the disease is required to select the right treatment. Therefore, in practice, the classification of MBS by etiology is used: it can be a primary myofascial pain syndrome, the root cause of which is direct damage to the muscle fiber - overstrain, microtears; as well as secondary MBS, the root cause in this case is pain in the joints, in the internal organs, in the spine.

For life, MBS is not dangerous, but to a large extent it can worsen its quality, reduce working capacity and accelerate the wear of bone and cartilage structures of the musculoskeletal system. Chronic pain syndrome exhausts a person physically, has a bad effect on the psycho-emotional state, and can disturb sleep. Lack of sleep increases fatigue, negatively affecting life and work activity.

Most of the pain in degenerative pathologies of the musculoskeletal system is caused by myofascial pain syndrome. Even if you remove the primary source of pain, with an already formed MBS, the pain will not go away, moreover, the incorrect distribution of loads in neighboring areas from the affected muscles will provoke micro traumatization and inflammation. Therefore, it is important to treat not only arthrosis of the joints, protrusions and hernias of the intervertebral discs, bursitis, synovitis, but also the surrounding muscles.

Reference:

1. Posner M. I. & Digirolamo G. J. Cognitive Neuroscience: Origins and Promise, Psychological Bulletin, - 2020, - no 126(6), - pp. 873—889.
2. Pirmanova, G. N., Yarkulovna, S. S., Najmiddinova, K. D., Mustafakulovich, I. A., & Shavkatovna, J. N. (2021). <https://doi.org/10.21744/lingcure.v5nS2.1716>
3. Zukhriddinova, Z. D. (2022). Development of Classification Criteria for Neuroretinal Ischemia in Arterial Hypertension. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL AND NATURAL SCIENCES, 3(3), 59-65. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/K76ZT>
4. Zuhridinova Z. D., Kamaljanovna M. D. DEVELOPMENT OF CLASSIFICATION CRITERIA FOR NEURORETINAL ISCHEMIA IN HYPERTENSION //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal.

- 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 02. – С. 972-978.
<https://wos.academiascience.org/index.php/wos/article/view/951/882>
5. Yuldashev S. S., Mamadaliev A. M., Aliev M. A. To Questions Of Surgical Tactics In Damagesof The Thoracic And Lumbar Parts Of The Spine //European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine. – 2020. – Т. 7. – №. 03. – С. 2020.
https://www.ejmcm.com/article_3419_20727dc3df7f4324cbcb048aa2f37c88.pdf
6. Bakhritdinov B.R, Aliev M.A, & Mardieva G.M. (2022). MULTIVOXEL MAGNETIC RESONANCE SPECTROSCOPY IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF BRAIN TUMORS. World Bulletin of Public Health, 8, 149-156. Retrieved from
<https://scholarexpress.net/index.php/wbph/article/view/738>
7. Mamadaliev A. M., Aliev M. A., Saidov K. D. The Research Of Different Methods Efficiency Of Posttraumatic Valve Defects Plasty //European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine. – 2020. – Т. 7. – №. 03. – С. 2020.
https://ejmcm.com/article_4676_1feec211fea5848f81258ea221dae974.pdf
8. Z. , Z. D. (2022). Rehabilitation and Treatment Algorithm for Patients with Ocular Ischemic Syndrome on the Background of Arterial Hypertension. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL AND NATURAL SCIENCES, 3(2), 211-213. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/SYA5K>
9. Zukhridinovna Z. D. MODERN ASPECTS OF NEUROPROTECTIVE TREATMENT IN HYPERTENSIVE RETINOPATHY //Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 02. – С. 949-952.
<https://wos.academiascience.org/index.php/wos/article/view/947/878>
10. Zukhriddinovna, Z. D. (2022). Clinical and Metabolic Peculiarities Children and Teenagers with Arterial Hypertension. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL AND NATURAL SCIENCES, 3(3), 177-184. Retrieved from
<https://cajmns.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJMNS/article/view/755>

11. Z. , Z. D., & K., M. D. (2022). Magnetic Resonance Tractography as a Method of Choice for Neuroimaging in Ocular Ischemic Syndrome against the Background of Hypertension. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL AND NATURAL SCIENCES, 3(2), 207-210.
<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/E2AH9>
12. D. Z, Z., Zh. B, E., & Z. Z, M. (2022). Changes Visual Systems at Patients with Essential Arterial Hypertension. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL AND NATURAL SCIENCES, 3(3), 744-750. Retrieved from
<https://cajmns.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJMNS/article/view/851>
13. Zuxridinovna, J. D. (2022). Ultrasonic Dopplerography of Retinal Vessels in Acute Cerebral Ischemia Against the Background of Arterial Hypertension. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL AND NATURAL SCIENCES, 3(3), 100-106. Retrieved from
<https://cajmns.centralasianstudies.org/index.php/CAJMNS/article/view/737>
14. Babayev, S. A., Bekturdiev, S. S., Rakhimov, N. M., Jalalova, D. Z., Yusupova, D. Z., & Shakhanova, S. S. (2021). ASSESSMENT OF THE STATE OF IMMUNITY IN PATIENTS WITH TUMORS. CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF MEDICAL AND NATURAL SCIENCES, 2(3), 218-225.
<https://doi.org/10.47494/cajmns.v2i3.204>